

Knowledge and attitudes to factory farming practices in the UK and US

Can minds and behaviour be changed?

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Executive summary

This report presents findings from a public opinion survey on factory farming conducted in the UK and US by Social Change Lab for [Project Slingshot](#). The research reveals significant public opposition to factory farming practices, despite the low salience of the issue. There are substantial knowledge gaps about most very common, current farming practices. However - a point of potential leverage - more accurate knowledge of these practices is associated with stronger opposition to them.

Key findings show that 56% of UK respondents and 45% of US respondents support a ban on factory farming; those who are neutral on the issue are similar in both countries (UK 22%, US 25%) meaning that relatively small minorities (UK 22%, US 30%) would oppose such a ban. These numbers are surprisingly consistent across all demographic and political groups. However, factory farming ranks very low in people's views of the nation's priorities, with just 1% naming it among the top three issues facing the country. The research identifies a key insight for mobilisation: the more people know about factory farming practices, the more they care and oppose factory farming. So both raising salience and improving knowledge about the prevalence of unacceptable practices are key to making progress. The group with the highest mobilisation potential, based on this research, are the health-conscious middle-classes.

Keywords: animal advocacy, animal agriculture, animal welfare, big agriculture, factory farming, farmed animal welfare, free-range, meat industry trust, organic farming, social movements

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Introduction

Despite decades of campaigning, animal advocates have largely failed to wake the public up to act against the horrors of factory farms. There is currently no mass movement for factory farm reform. All the while, billions of animals suffer daily in horrific conditions. This situation needs to urgently change and this survey is a small contribution to support that change. Its purpose is to understand where the public stands on factory farming, both as a general concept but also in terms of their attitudes and knowledge of specific widespread practices that produce the meat they consume. Where are the points of leverage for mobilisation? Who are the key groups to target? How can minds and behaviours be changed? These are some of the key questions that [Project Slingshot](http://projectslingshot.com/)¹, which commissioned this survey, seeks to answer.

Project Slingshot is a major new initiative which aims to expose the truth about factory farming and start building the movement to end it. Insights from this survey will inform

¹ <http://projectslingshot.com/>

their 2026 campaign. With their agreement and support, we are making the insights from this research freely available and open to other groups working to end animal suffering, as well as to the public more broadly.

Understanding where the public is at is essential for organisations working to reduce the harms associated with intensive animal agriculture, whether those groups focus on improving the lives of farmed animals or focus on ending factory farming. The research sought to move beyond simple support metrics to identify specific psychological and informational barriers that might be stalling wider public engagement with this issue.

We know from [recent surveys](#) that there is consistently strong public opposition to factory farming practices in both the UK and US, though significant knowledge gaps persist. In the UK, a 2024 [Bryant Research survey](#) showed people dramatically underestimate the prevalence of intensive farming, with the public estimating that only 58% of all farmed animals and 68% of chickens are factory farmed when the actual percentages for both are well over 90%. In the US, the most recent 2025 [Faunalytics survey](#) found overwhelming disapproval of specific practices, with 82-85% opposing confinement methods like battery cages, gestation crates and crowded barns. A 2023 [ASPCA survey](#) conducted by Ipsos found 79% concerned about industrial agriculture's impact on animal welfare, and 74% supporting a ban on new factory farms.

Across both countries, when people are informed about specific factory farming practices, large majorities find them unacceptable, but public awareness of how widespread these practices actually are remains surprisingly low.

This research builds on that knowledge, reinforcing some key findings and providing more detailed information on specific knowledge gaps - both of the industry and of particular practices.

Research questions

The survey explored three core questions:

- How do people currently view factory farming and the industry that produces it?
- What do they actually know about standard farming practices?
- Where might there be opportunities to shift public opinion and policy?

Key findings

1. People do not like factory farms

Public sentiment towards factory farming is overwhelmingly negative. Most people believe factory farms have a detrimental environmental impact and view them as poorly regulated with inadequate welfare standards. The strength of opposition is striking, with at least 73% of UK respondents opposing chickens, pigs and dairy cows being reared in factory farms and 56% supporting an outright ban on factory farming.

Figure 1: Public attitudes toward factory farming statements (UK)

When presented with specific statements about factory farming, the public's views are pretty clear. The vast majority agree that society needs to fundamentally change how we treat animals for food and they don't believe that factory farms are well-regulated. This disapproval is not confined to a particular demographic or political group; support for a factory farming ban spans party lines; in the UK, it is perhaps unsurprising that 76% of Green party voters support a ban - but this figure is 48% for Reform voters - signalling an

unusual degree of agreement in an otherwise divided political landscape. People across age groups and even dietary habits show majority support for a ban.

Figure 2: Support for banning factory farming in the UK (left) and US (right)

The general public does believe that factory farms are effective at keeping costs down. This highlights a tension in public attitudes between affordability concerns and ethical objections, particularly at a time when cost of living concerns are extremely high for many people. Even if people want to 'do the right thing' they feel unable to when the cost of high welfare animal products are so much greater. [Studies show](#) that organic meat such as chicken typically costs double the price of non-organic equivalents - in part because the cost of factory farmed meat is [artificially low](#), since externalities such as the pollution caused by farms and the knock-on consequences of antibiotic resistance, are not included in prices.

2. Very few people trust the factory farming industry

Despite the fact that most people purchase and consume animal products from factory farms on a daily basis, trust in the meat industry is remarkably low. Only 5% of people think the meat industry takes very good care of animal welfare, and just 3% believe that labels accurately reflect how animals are treated. When asked about industry communications, two-thirds of respondents consider them untrustworthy, with just 2% saying they "completely trust" what the industry says about animal welfare.

Knowledge and attitudes to factory farming practices in the UK and US

Figure 3: Trust in meat industry communications about animal welfare UK (left) and US (right)

But of course there is a big difference between what we say we explicitly believe when asked, and the compound effects of the highly misleading visual messaging we are surrounded by.

Figure 4: Examples of animal product packaging showing contented animals living their best outdoor life

As well as a deficit of trust in the industry, there is a striking lack of knowledge about who its main players are; when asked to name factory farming companies, most people could not name a single one. The most cited company, Bernard Matthews in the UK, actually a subsidiary of a larger group, was named by only 8% of respondents; Arla was named by around 3% and the others named (Moy Park, Cranswick, Tyson, 2 sisters, Avara, Muller, Cargill and JBS) were named by 1% or fewer respondents. In the US, there was greater knowledge of the main players: 36% of respondents named Tyson, 20% Perdue/Purdue (spelling varied), 5% Smithfield and the remainder (Cargill, Foster Farms, Hormel, Sanderson Farms, Pilgrims Pride and JBS) were named by fewer than 3% of people. This

combination of distrust and anonymity suggests the industry operates largely unscrutinised, another potential point of leverage as we will discuss later.

3. And they don't even know how bad things are

Perhaps the most significant finding is the scale of public ignorance about actual factory farming practices. People dramatically overestimate the prevalence of high-welfare practices and significantly underestimate low-welfare ones. These knowledge gaps are consistent across multiple practices.

For example, [95% of calves](#) in dairy production are separated from their mothers within 24 hours of birth (based on French data, though this practice is widespread across Europe). The public's estimate of this practice is just 59.5%, a gap of 35.5 percentage points. Similarly, [88% of pigs](#) in England and Wales are killed using CO2 gas stunning, a practice many experts consider inhumane. The public estimated this figure at only 53.6%, a 34.4 point gap. People thought that 71% of chicken sold in the UK comes from factory farms; [the reality is 95%](#) - a 24 point gap.

Public underestimates prevalence of low-welfare practices

Blue = what people think | Red = reality

Figure 5: Public underestimates prevalence of low-welfare practices

These knowledge gaps are even more pronounced in the US data, suggesting that public education campaigns could have substantial impact. The disconnect between public

assumptions and farming realities represents a significant opportunity for carefully designed communication by advocates.

People also overestimate the prevalence of high welfare practices. For example, people think that nearly a third (29.6%) of pigs are raised organically; [the real proportion is less than 1%](#). People thought a similar number (31.5%) of chickens are free-range; [the real proportion is 3.5%](#). These gaps, a result of big agriculture's deliberate and successful strategies to present fictions about the welfare of farmed animals, help contribute to people's sense that their own consumption practices reflect higher welfare practices.

Public overestimates prevalence of high-welfare farming

Red = reality | Blue = what people think

Figure 6: Public overestimates prevalence of high-welfare practices

4. When they are told about bad practices, the great majority of people find them unacceptable

As we know from other surveys both [in the US](#) and [in the UK](#), when people are presented with information about standard factory farming practices, public opposition is marked. In the survey, we tested reactions to 12 common practices in different animals, providing information about their prevalence. (Practices were randomised so participants saw them in different orders.) For chickens, these were hock burn ulcers from ammonia, beak

trimming without pain relief, A4-sized spaces, killing of male chicks and the low percentage of broiler chickens raised free-range. For pigs, they were piglet thumping, use of farrowing crates for pregnant pigs, and CO2 gas stunning. For cows, they were calf separation, the presence of pus cells in milk and early slaughter of dairy cows. We also described the slaughter of conscious sheep. The results showed that very large majorities (the range was 75% to 94%) found every practice unacceptable.

Public finds factory farming practices unacceptable

Percentage who rate each practice as 'unacceptable' or 'totally unacceptable'

Figure 7: Vast majority of people find factory farming practices unacceptable (UK)

The consistency of these findings is notable. Whether the practice involves chickens, pigs, cattle or sheep, and regardless of whether respondents eat meat regularly or not, opposition remains strong. This suggests that public opinion, when properly informed,

strongly favours significant reforms to current farming practices.

Public finds factory farming practices unacceptable

Percentage who rate each practice as 'unacceptable' or 'totally unacceptable'

Figure 8: Vast majority of people find factory farming practices unacceptable (US)

5. But factory farming is mostly not on people's minds. Even though disapproval is high, salience is low

Despite the strong disapproval of factory farming practices, the issue barely registers in public consciousness as a priority. When asked to name the top three issues facing the country, just 1% of respondents mentioned factory farming. By contrast, the economy was named by 71%, immigration and asylum by 55%, and health by 46%.

When it comes to factory farming, people care when prompted, but factory farming doesn't spontaneously come to mind as a pressing issue. So the first challenge is not even about

changing minds - it's about bringing the issue to mind in the first place.

Figure 9: What the public think are the most important issues facing the country in the UK (left) and the US (right)

This low salience creates both a challenge and an opportunity. The challenge is self-explanatory: it is difficult to mobilise the public on issues that are not on their minds. Politicians respond to what they perceive as voter priorities, and factory farming currently isn't one. However, the gap between strong disapproval and low salience also represents an opportunity; we know the public aren't indifferent to the harms of factory farming, so perhaps they just haven't been sufficiently confronted with the reality of it. Once they are aware, their existing values around care for animals give advocates something concrete to build on.

6. So where is the leverage?

The evidence points to three places to gain traction:

1. Increasing the visibility of the harms of factory farming - closing the gap between what people think goes on and what actually does.
2. Increasing a sense of urgency about doing something about it, making it a more

pressing issue - one that can compete more effectively with other public concerns.

3. Bring the 'big ag' corporations into the light. Identifying a clear adversary opens up tactical possibilities (as [we have shown](#) with fossil fuel companies) and in an era of distrust in institutions, these huge corporations could be seen as legitimate targets.

Our analysis shows that the more accurately people understand actual farming practices, the more likely they are to support a factory farming ban. This correlation is statistically significant across multiple practices. This finding - that the more people know, the more they care - is one of the most important findings of this survey.

Figure 11: Accurate knowledge increases support for reform (US data).

This effect is strongest for certain practices: separation of calves from their mothers, CO₂ gas stunning of pigs and fecal contamination of chickens.

Figure 12: Accurate knowledge of specific practices increases support for reform more strongly (US data)

The research also identifies specific groups that appear more influenceable. In segmentation analyses, we examined two key demographics: health-conscious, educated middle classes, and progressive youth².

In both the UK and US, health-conscious, well-educated, middle class respondents have more knowledge of factory farming practices and are more opposed to and skeptical of farming practices than the average person. They have higher than average concern about antibiotic use and show greater support for bans on factory farming across all animals. These factors make them potentially valuable advocates.

² The first group were represented by people who have degrees, whose chief income earner is in an (upper) middle class profession, who are infrequent meat purchasers and/or favourable to alternative proteins and who consider vegetables healthy. The second group were represented by those under 36 who vote Labour, Liberal Democrats, Greens, SNP, or Plaid Cymru (UK) or Democrat (US).

Health-conscious (upper) middle class vs Others: Key Metrics			
This segment is consistently more aware, concerned, and skeptical of industry practices			
Metric	Health-conscious (upper) middle (%)	Others (%)	Difference (pp)
Oppose raising dairy cows in FFs	81.4	70.0	11.4
Oppose raising chickens in FFs	79.3	68.4	10.9
Oppose raising pigs in FFs	80.8	70.1	10.7
Support factory farming ban	61.4	51.8	9.6
Highly concerned about antibiotics	47.2	41.1	6.1
Can name FF companies	21.5	18.5	3.0
Overall knowledge accuracy	69.7	67.5	2.2
Trust labels	33.3	36.8	-3.5
Perceive chicken as healthy	81.1	85.7	-4.6
Perceive red meat as healthy	36.0	46.8	-10.8

Difference = Ethical Consumers - Others (percentage points)

Social Change Lab • UK Public Opinion on Factory Farming

Figure

Figure 13: Health conscious middle classes show greater opposition to factory farming (UK figures)

We also theorised that ‘progressive youth’ would be a relatively mobilisable demographic. This turned out to be more true of the US than the UK. In the UK, progressive youth do oppose factory farming, but they show lower levels of support compared to older progressives and are less mobilised by the issue than might be expected.

Figure 14: Young people in the UK generally show lower opposition to factory farming than older people

In the US, we did not see this same trend, with young progressives showing overall opposition to factory farming at more expected levels - though even here, they are outdone by older progressives. Progressive youth also found practices more unacceptable relative to other respondents.

Figure 15: Progressive youth in the US find all factory farming practices more unacceptable than other demographics.

Recommendations

Here we summarise some of the key lessons from this and other similar research for the animal advocacy movement and provide recommendations:

- **Tell it like it is.** The key strategic insight is that increasing salience must go hand in hand with **information** - telling the facts about factory farming practices. The public already has the values and the disgust response. Campaigns that can raise awareness while educating about the disturbing everyday realities have the potential to shift how people see this issue, and hopefully create momentum for policy reform. Although animal advocates are familiar with public distaste for factory farms and believe it is just a matter of raising the salience of this issue, our data suggest that it is still really important to improve public knowledge and understanding. This must clearly be done with care, due to the risk that excessive detail about awful practices might make people turn away.
- **Know who you are talking to.** Advocacy strategies need to be tailored differently

to respond to different country and demographic characteristics. For example, antibiotic resistance is a much bigger concern in the UK than in the US; US progressive youth seem a more obvious target group than their counterparts in the UK.

- **Name and shame.** Big ag companies are mostly living in the shadows, hidden from view, just like most factory farms. Bringing both into the light offers campaigners and activists a range of new tactical approaches. The public already has a high level of distrust of meat industry messaging which could be better harnessed.
- **There's more to do on misleading packaging.** It is illegal to deliberately mislead and use false claims in advertising. Several successful lawsuits have been brought against meat and dairy companies for false claims about [pasture raised eggs](#), ['climate-smart' beef](#) and many more untruths. Such cases are likely to have public support given the high levels of existing distrust - and can be financially and reputationally costly for big ag companies.
- **Being disgusted is easy.** But it is still a long way from changing daily consumption behaviours. We did not address this question here, but an important next step is to turn emotions into tangible actions, for example researching which behaviour change tools (alternative proteins, default menus, meat taxes) are the most effective in making people's concerns visible in their actions.

Methodology

The survey was conducted online in November 2025 by Social Change Lab. The UK sample comprised 1,972 respondents and the US sample 1,949 respondents. Both samples were designed to be nationally representative of the adult population in age, gender, region of residence, ethnicity, political affiliation, education, and household income. The survey was carried out on the [Qualtrics](#) survey platform and participants were recruited on [Prolific](#).

The survey included questions measuring attitudes towards factory farming, knowledge of farming practices, trust in the meat industry, support for policy interventions, and various demographic and behavioural variables. Questions about farming practices included both measures of perceived practices (what people think happens) and presentation of factual information about actual prevalence rates.

Segmentation analysis was conducted on both the UK and US datasets, focusing on two predefined segments: health-conscious educated people in the upper middle class, and

progressive youth. These segments were identified based on combinations of demographic variables, dietary behaviours, and political orientation. The analyses examined how these groups differed from the general population in their attitudes towards factory farming and related issues.

Regression analysis examined relationships between knowledge accuracy (measured as the gap between perceived and actual prevalence of practices) and support for banning factory farming.

Supplementary materials

Detailed findings from the survey, including full breakdowns by demographic groups and additional analyses, are available on request.

These supplementary materials include additional data on topics such as perceived health impacts of different foods, awareness of specific farming companies, attitudes across different animal species, and detailed demographic breakdowns of all major findings. The segmentation analyses provide further insights into the characteristics, attitudes and mobilisation potential of key demographic groups.

For questions about this research or to access the complete dataset, please contact info@socialchangelab.org.

About Social Change Lab

[Social Change Lab](#) conducts empirical research on people-powered social movements. Through research reports, workshops, and training, we provide actionable insights to help movements and funders be more effective. You can find all of our research projects and resources on [our website](#).